

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGICAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract: The article discusses the problems of improving the quality of education, their solutions and prospects, including improving curricula, designing training, organizing research in accordance with the requirements of the time, using foreign experience, professional qualities and development of logical thinking operations, etc.

Key words: science, education, upbringing, curriculum, state educational standard, knowledge, skills, competence, professional quality, logical thinking, method, technology.

INTRODUCTION. It is known that the training of qualified specialists who contribute to the socio-economic development of the country directly depends on the development of the education system, and in this regard, the education of an independently thinking, creative, enterprising, enterprising individual is a priority task. public policy remains one of his complaints today. These tasks are reflected in a number of decrees and resolutions [1-10] of the President of our republic.

LITERARY ANALYSIS AND METHODS. We will consider and analyze the opinions of the following scientists on improving the quality of education in our republic: advanced pedagogical technologies and interactive methods based on them, improving the system for assessing results, organizing and implementing all its forms, taking into account new technical and technological achievements, independent thinking, and the creative abilities of students and formation of their

professional skills at the level of modern requirements, create a continuous connection between educational training and non-traditional studies and research work, arouse professional and economic interests, independently collect the necessary information, to solve the problem it is necessary to focus on a systematic and creative approach to identifying, finding solutions, critically analyzing the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities and applying them to solve new problems [11 -18]. If the teacher can explain that the topic is based on important theory and that the ideas are logically connected, he will achieve a certain goal. To do this, it is necessary to use the capabilities and methods of modern teaching technologies [19].

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. In order to improve the quality of education, teachers must adapt their knowledge and professional skills to the requirements of the time, use innovative educational technologies in teaching, use pedagogical and information technologies of each subject for the effectiveness of organized lessons, as well as for the student. To study well, it is necessary to ensure its completion. One of the urgent tasks is to introduce into practice education based on a competency-based approach to learning, the ability to apply acquired knowledge in life, choose a profession, receive independent education, and develop educational and cognitive competencies [20-23].

Today in our republic important and worthy work is being carried out to modernize the education system, introduce innovative teaching technologies, train young people with such professional qualities as independence, creativity, initiative, entrepreneurship, and encouragement of teachers.

However, analysis and research show that problems still exist in our education system.

Including:

- lack of qualified teachers in educational institutions, the fact that reforms in the field are not fully taken into account when creating curricula and programs implemented in their training, and they are outdated in content;

- lack of systematic and innovative activities to strengthen the theoretical and practical knowledge of students and implement the creative ideas of talented youth;
- that teachers do not organize training sessions aimed at developing the intellectual abilities of students;
- lack of widespread implementation by teachers of innovative pedagogical technologies and methods;
- mutual cooperation between educational institutions is not fully established;
- students are rarely given the opportunity to argue and express their opinions during the training; the fact that teachers are limited to repeating old information in some classes, at the level of their needs [24].

Lack of training, low levels of knowledge and skills remain a serious problem, and competencies are perceived as insufficient.

Addressing these issues requires regular training of educators, the use of alternative methods, and implementation of tasks such as continuous research. This, in turn, places greater responsibility on the teacher.

Today, great changes are taking place in the social and economic spheres. A lot of new equipment and technologies and investments are coming to our republic from abroad; in addition, they are produced in our country, new enterprises and production organizations are being created. Of course, tomorrow they will need a specialist who can work independently and manage them. That is why today we are preparing our specialists for the future, studying the modern qualification requirements they require clearly, correctly, without working in the style of “from us to the owner,” and, if necessary, at this enterprise.

It is necessary to go to organizations, see them with your own eyes and form them together with leading and experienced specialists. The requirements of this completed qualification must be reflected in the curriculum;

- bringing the distribution of hours for current educational programs in the form of a table. It is desirable that the distribution of subject hours in the curriculum be

reflected in the curriculum. Because when a teacher opens a program, he does not look for a clock or refer to the curriculum. This makes work easier and saves time;

- we observe that interactive methods, such as brainstorming, boomerang, syncway, concept table, are recorded in the curriculum as the use of modern pedagogical and information technologies in teaching science. After all, these are not pedagogical technologies, these are interactive methods created on the basis of pedagogical technologies. As for information technology, the name of the technology is not written. So this is the wrong approach and interpretation. Therefore, to eliminate such shortcomings, you need to pay attention to the following:

- as modern pedagogical technologies used in pedagogical science:
- aimed at ensuring the social and cognitive activity of the student - personal and humanitarian;
- a complete representation of the technological level of the educational process, focused on implementation - design;
- problem-based learning aimed at developing the competence of independence, initiative, entrepreneurship, cooperation, creativity;
- focus on heuristic learning aimed at developing the student's creativity and innovation.

CONCLUSION. In implementing these tasks, it is necessary to effectively use foreign experience in training qualified specialists and, on its basis, develop new approaches to organizing training in educational institutions. Since the educational process is the main area of pedagogical creativity, and a correct, innovative approach to its organization and management allows students to gain knowledge, independence, creativity, initiative, cooperation, deepening professional competencies, and draws attention to the quality of education[25].

Eliminating existing shortcomings and problems in improving the quality of education, clearly defining goals and objectives in this way, using world-recognized

experience, using information technology in combination with pedagogical technologies to improve the quality of professional training of future specialists serves to improve the efficiency of the process. Clarification of educational goals, the use of various technologies and methods used in the processes of learning and development, focus on content leads to the development and improvement of the activities of educational institutions[26].

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